

Artificial Intelligence Versus Human Intelligence, Who Will Win?

OPEN ACCESS

Volume : 6

Special Issue : 1

Month : August

Year: 2018

ISSN: 2321-788X

Impact Factor: 3.025

Citation:

Ambekar, Archana, et al. “Artificial Intelligence Versus Human Intelligence, Who Will Win?” *Shanlax International Journal of Arts, Science and Humanities*, vol. 6, no. S1, 2018, pp. 34–37.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1403569>

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Abstract

Artificial Intelligence is referred to intelligence demonstrated by Machines. It is the area of computer science which stimulates intelligence in the machines and programme the machines to think and mimic the way a person acts and reacts. Artificial Intelligence today is known as Narrow or weak Artificial Intelligence and its outcome is quantum computing, SIRI the friendly voice activated computer Robotics, virtual personal assistance, video gaming smart car, predictions, fraud detections etc.

Artificial Intelligence from its narrow approach is rapidly progressing towards General or Strong Approach that is from self-driving cars to Machines playing chess and solving puzzles.

An important question now that arises is, what will happen if the Strong Artificial Intelligence Succeeds? Many researchers have expressed concern and fear over this issue. The same researchers believe that the Artificial Intelligence will help to build a strong future but will also lead Artificial intelligence toward s becoming potentially more stronger than their Creators that is more stronger than the Humans.

People now control the planet not because they are Strongest, fastest or Biggest but because we are Smartest. If we are no longer the smartest then we will remain under Control of the smart Machines.

Our Civilization will flourish as long as we win the race between Growing power of technology and the wisdom with which we manage it.

Keywords; Intelligentmachines, narrow approach, strong approach, creators, control and manage.

Introduction

The Dooms Day s Theory Says that “Artificial Intelligence and the Machines will one fine day destroy the Mankind.”

Stephen Hawking has also warned the world about the development of robots and the machines beyond a certain point that will end the Mankind.

Some experts have also expressed their thoughts over the development of Artificial Intelligence and its negative consequence in the near future of our World.

Similarly there are various Scientists, Innovators and Experts

in the field of Artificial Intelligence who are promoting the development of the Computers and Machines for the betterment of the Mankind towards Prosperous Future of our word and Stating the benefits of Artificial Intelligence in all the spheres of life and all the other sector including Business, Industries, Education, Health Care etc.

From the above it can be summarized that there are conflicting ideas about the concept of Artificial Intelligence and the conflict is because some experts give more weightage to Human Intelligence when compared to the Artificial Intelligence.

Objective

- To study both the types of intelligence, and express our idea on their differences and our personalized opinion on which is better and which is ultimately going to Win.

Conceptual Frame Work

Artificial Intelligence

It is related to creation of Intelligent Machines. These Machines have ability to create a never ending thought process that would help in solving all the problems.

By inventing revolutionary new Technologies such super-intelligence might help in eradicating war, diseases and poverty.

Human Intelligence

It is related to natural intelligence among the humans. This intelligence has ability to adapt, and learn from all the situations which helps to solve all problems and lead towards evolution of human brain.

An important question is what will happen if the quest for the strong Artificial Intelligence succeeds and what if Artificial Intelligence system becomes better and stronger?

To comment on “WHO WILL WIN”? We will have to compare both Artificial Intelligence and Human Intelligence.

Comparison of Artificial Intelligence and Human Intelligence

Features of Artificial Intelligence

1. As name suggests it is artificial in nature.
2. It is a stimulated intelligence in machines in the form of a program
3. It is result of revolutionary Invention.
4. It works on Digital Data.
5. It is of two types Narrow and General.
6. It has tremendous speed of execution.
7. It is less biased.
8. It has exceptional Operational Ability.
9. It is extremely accurate.
10. It has good Memory.
11. It works on hard ware and software.
12. It performs limited task.
13. It requires supervision and maintenance.
14. It is vulnerable to virus.
15. It does not take any responsibility.

The above mentioned features of Artificial Intelligence includes both the benefits as well as the limitations. we believe that today Artificial Intelligence will help us to better prepare and prevent potential negative consequences in the future thus enjoying the benefits while avoiding pitfalls. Artificial Intelligence has the potential to become more intelligent than their Creators and thus control the humans and the planet. All systems are as good as the data if we enter poor data the system can become racial, gender or ideological biased which may continue to be trained using bad data making it an ongoing problem.

It is here, the Human Intelligence will become important, and eliminate the errors caused due to the computers and machines.

Features of Human Intelligence.

1. It is natural as it is the result of the evolution of brain.
2. It is genetically inherited.
3. It increases with learning and experience.
4. It adapts and evolves with interpersonal contacts and communication.
5. It depends on the mental qualities.
6. It is capable of improvising on its own.
7. It has reasoning and problem solving capacity.
8. It has rational thinking and self-motivating ability.
9. It is creative in planning and execution.
10. It has self-awareness and manipulative skills.
11. It can manage different skills during life time.
12. It creates and dominates Artificial Intelligence.
13. It can identify and address various opportunities.
14. It can cope with situations.
15. It is of different types like Naturalist, Musical Linguisticetc.

All the limitations of the human beings apply as the limitations to the human intelligence. But all of which can be overcome. The Humans should bear in mind that the scale of problem in Artificial Intelligence can be exponential, our energy source and ability to observe the world is always finite and thus the result in terms of ordinary human experience are likely less impressive than they sound.

Findings

Technology is emerging day by day Scientists are more and more interested in making something innovative Artificial Intelligence and robots are being joined, computer and machines are created that are synonymous to both humans and animals by efforts employed together. The major aim of Artificial Intelligence is to add human qualities in robotics so that they become more human.

Our Civilization will definitely flourish as we remain the Smartest, Ethical and the most responsible. As the two sides of the same coin both the Artificial Intelligence and the Human Intelligence have both Strengths and Weakness. The qualities like having Moral values being Ethical, feeling bad, guilty, being scared and fear of God are always going to take us towards a brighter future. Yes we need help and support that can be obtained from Artificial Intelligence, TOO much of reliance and over-dependency on AI will definitely create problems that is where the Experts feel that AI will become more stronger than us and control us. Experience make each person different but that is not exactly how AI works, it works on its algorithms, different types of digital data, built in instructions designed by the Scientists, discarding Culture and preference. Seen at the macro level improvement

in AI would create a loss of identity where human intelligence experience of both driver and the customer is overridden by a machine. In simple words a human has been displaced by Artificial Intelligence. We may not accept it but this is in essence, a machine planning what is best for a human.

Conclusion

The humans are the creators of Artificial intelligence hence it is up to them how to processed with the progression and the development of the Artificial Intelligence. Till date we have very intelligently utilized the efficiency, speed and accuracy of the Machines.

From mining to going to Mars Artificial intelligence has assisted us to discover new Frontiers. Artificial Intelligence is the beginning of a human Machine Partnership that should start off with coming together of many minds-sociologists, Scientists and engineers who must deliberate on the effect of Artificial on communities and individuals. The major aim in development of Artificial Intelligence should not be to add human qualities in robotics rather leave them as machines so that they do not become like humans and compete with them and thus avoiding devastating effects. SO the answer to the question Who Will WIN? Is definitely we 'Humans will win'. We will remain to be the Remote Control of the Machines and never be controlled by them.

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